

Synthesis, spectral, thermal and electrochemical studies of iron(III) complexes with 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(4-methoxy-2-phenol azo)-5-pyrazolone and 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(3-methoxy-2-phenol azo)-5-pyrazolone

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Abstract : Some novel iron(III) complexes of formulae $[\text{FeL}_1(\text{X})_3]$, $[\text{FeL}_1(\text{Y})(\text{X})_2]$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{L}_1)_2(\text{Z})\text{X}]$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{L}_2)_2(\text{X})_2]\text{X}$, $[\text{FeL}_2(\text{X})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$, $[\text{FeL}_2(\text{Y})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{X}]$, $[\text{FeL}_2(\text{Z})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$, $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{L}_2)_2(\text{X})_6]$ (where $\text{L}_1 = \text{GAAP}$, guaiacolazoantipyrine; $\text{L}_2 = \text{MPAAP}$, 3-methoxy phenol azo antipyrine; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}/\text{Br}/\text{NO}_3$; $\text{Y} = \text{NCS}$; $\text{Z} = \text{ClO}_4$) have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility data and spectral (IR, UV-Visible, ^1H NMR and FAB-mass) studies. The thermal behaviour of one of the complexes was investigated by thermogravimetric techniques. The X-ray diffraction studies of the complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{MPAAP})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$ indicated orthorhombic crystal lattice with unit cell dimensions, $a = 6.0330 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 7.3207 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 12.8374 \text{ \AA}$. The electrochemical properties of the complex $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{MPAAP})_2\text{Cl}_6]$ were investigated by cyclic voltammetry. An octahedral structure is tentatively proposed for the complexes.

Keywords : Iron(III), dyes, thermal studies.

Introduction

The common oxidation states of iron are +2 and +3. Almost all the aqueous chemistry of iron is confined to the +2 and +3 oxidation states. Fe^{III} iron forms a large number of complexes than Fe^{II} ion. In most of these, the coordination number of Fe^{3+} ion is six and the complexes formed are octahedral¹. However, a few complexes in which the coordination number is four and the structure is tetrahedral are also known. Fe^{III} ion has a strong tendency to form complexes with ligands which coordinate via oxygen. Ion(III) with d^5 configuration has ground state $^6A_{1g}$ in an octahedral field arising out of free ion term 6S . Iron(III) complexes are typical examples for spin cross overs and high spin-low spin equilibrium. Five coordinate complexes of iron(III) can be high spin or low spin depending on the nature of the ligands^{1,2}.

Azo dyes play an important role in fabrication from olden days itself. Some metal complexes of azo dyes are used in photography. For the dyeing of polyamide fibres, certain metal complexes of azo dyes were found to be effective³.

In view of these factors, we have prepared and characterized a few new complexes of iron(III) with the poten-

tial multidentate ligands 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(3-methoxy-2-phenol azo)-5-pyrazolone, guaiacolazoantipyrine, GAAP (Fig. 1a) and 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(4-methoxy-2-phenol azo)-5-pyrazolone, 3-methoxy phenol azo antipyrine, MPAAP (Fig. 1b).

Fig. 1a. GAAP

Fig. 1b. MPAAP

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of Fe^{III} complexes

Complexes/ H ^{eff} (Colour)	Analytical data (%): Found : (Calcd.)							Molar conductance in nitrobenzene	
	Metal	Cl/Br	C	H	N	S	(Ω^{-1} cm ² mol ⁻¹)	(B.M.)	
[Fe(GAAP)Cl ₃] (Brown)	11.7 (11.1)	20.8 (21.2)	39.5 (43.1)	4.71 (3.6)	10.40 (11.20)		6.9	4.72	
[Fe(GAAP)(NCS)Cl ₂] (Black)	10.7 (10.6)	13.5 (13.5)	40.2 (43.6)	3.7 (3.4)	12.8 (13.3)	8.9 (6.2)	2.2	4.88	
[Fe(GAAP)(NO ₃) ₃] (Black)	9.4 (9.6)	-	36.2 (37.2)	3.8 (3.1)	16.4 (16.9)		1.2	4.5	
[Fe(GAAP)Br ₃] (Brown)	9.03 (8.8)	39.1 (37.8)	36.0 (34.0)	4.2 (2.8)	9.0 (8.8)		1.3	4.15	
[Fe(GAAP) ₂ (ClO ₄)Cl](ClO ₄) (Black)	5.8 (5.7)	11.0 (11.0)	45.5 (44.7)	3.0 (3.7)	13.8 (11.5)		22	4.44	
[Fe ₂ (MPAAP) ₂ Cl ₆] (Black)	11.3 (11.1)	20.2 (21.2)	39.9 (43.1)	3.5 (3.6)	10.3 (11.2)		2.2	2.3	
[Fe(MPAAP)(NCS) ₂ (H ₂ O)Cl] (Brown)	10.3 (9.9)	6.3 (6.3)	43.4 (42.6)	2.9 (3.5)	14.3 (14.9)	10.7 (11.3)	2.8	5.67	
[Fe(MPAAP)(NO ₃) ₃ (H ₂ O)] (Brown)	9.5 (9.3)	-	38.2 (36.1)	3.2 (3.3)	16.6 (16.4)		2.3	4.45	
[Fe(MPAAP) ₂ Br ₂]Br (Black)	5.8 (5.7)	24.3 (24.6)	46.9 (44.4)	5.2 (3.7)	12.1 (11.5)		23	4.15	
[Fe(MPAAP)(ClO ₄) ₂ (H ₂ O)] (Brown)	7.9 (7.8)	14.9 (14.9)	30.0 (30.4)	2.6 (2.8)	8.3 (7.9)		4	5.95	

Results and discussion

All the complexes are dark coloured, non-hygroscopic solids. They are soluble in nitrobenzene and acetonitrile and sparingly soluble in other common organic solvents. The analytical data are in agreement with the compositions proposed for the complexes in Table 1. The molar conductance data (Table 1) show that all the complexes are non-electrolytes except a perchlorato and a bromo complex^{4,5}. The magnetic moments (Table 1) of iron(III) complexes are in the range 4.15–5.95 B.M. at room temperature. Diamagnetic corrections, χ_{Dia} were computed using Pascal's constants² ($\chi_{\text{Dia}} = -13.8 \times 10^{-6}$ C.G.S. units for Fe^{3+}). For a high spin octahedral iron complex¹, the μ_{eff} value is 5.9 B.M. The lower values in the complexes are intermediate between those corresponding to high spin and low spin complexes. It can be attributed to the existence of spin free ($S = 5/2$) $\text{Fe}^{3+} \leftrightarrow$ spin free ($S = 1/2$) Fe^{3+} equilibrium in an octahedral crystal field⁶⁻⁸. This thermal equilibrium is temperature dependent^{6,7}. The low μ_{eff} value 2.3 B.M. of one of the complexes is also due to high metal-metal interaction².

Table 2 lists selected vibrational bands and assignments of ligands and their iron(III) complexes. The infrared spectra of free ligands GAAP and MPAAP, a broad medium intensity band ~ 3103 and 3062 cm^{-1} respectively is assignable to hydrogen bonded -OH group¹¹.

The medium broad band observed $\sim 3103 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in GAAP disappeared in the spectra of all the complexes,

instead a new band appeared $\sim 3170 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting the participation of -OH group in the complex formation without deprotonation. This clearly indicates that the hydrogen bond is broken during complexation and hence its participation in coordination with the metal ion. But in MPAAP complexes, the medium broad band $\sim 3062 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ disappears and a new broad band $\sim 3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ appears in all the complexes, suggesting the non participation of -OH group in coordination with metal ion¹¹.

Very strong bands at ~ 1637 and 1645 cm^{-1} respectively in the IR spectra of these ligands are attributed to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of the pyrazolone ring. These are shifted to lower frequencies from 1612 cm^{-1} to 1564 cm^{-1} in all the complexes showing the evidence for participation of (C=O) group in complexation⁴.

Also, another band of medium intensity observed ~ 1458 and 1456 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra of the ligands have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{N=N}}$ group¹⁰. It is shifted to lower frequency (20 to 43 cm^{-1}) in the spectra of all the complexes, suggesting the participation of azo group in coordination with the metal ion¹².

Thus the ligand GAAP acts as neutral tridentate chelating agent in all the complexes except in perchlorato complex. The ligand MPAAP acts as a neutral bidentate chelating agent in its complexes.

Table 2 lists selected vibrational bands and assignments of the ligands and their metal complexes. The IR

Table 2. Spectral data of the ligands GAAP and MPAAP and its iron(III) complexes

Ligands/ Complexes	Infrared spectra (cm^{-1})								
	ν_{OH} (Hydrogen bonded)	ν_{OH} (Coordinated/free)	ν_{OH} (H_2O)	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{N=N}}$	ν_{NCS}	$\nu_{\text{Fe-O}}$ (H_2O)	$\nu_{\text{Fe-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{Fe-O}}$
GAAP	3103 mb	–	–	1637 vs	1458 s	–	–	–	–
[Fe(GAAP)Cl ₃]	–	3167 s	–	1612 vs	1419 s	–	503 m	443 m	–
[Fe(GAAP)(NCS)Cl ₂]	–	3182 s	–	1589 vs	1423 s	2050 vs	507 m	441 m	–
[Fe(GAAP)(NO ₃) ₃]	–	3170 s	–	1598 vs	1429 s	–	503 m	445 m	–
[Fe(GAAP)Br ₃]	–	3172 s	–	1581 vs	1444 s	–	547 m	507 m	–
[Fe(GAAP) ₂ (ClO ₄)Cl]ClO ₄	–	3423 mb	–	1564 vs	1433 s	–	445 m	383 m	–
MPAAP	3062 mb	–	–	1645 vs	1456 s	–	–	–	–
[Fe ₂ (MPAAP) ₂ C ₆] (Black)	–	3404 mb	–	1592 vs	1442 s	–	470 m	439 m	–
[Fe(MPAAP)(NCS) ₂ (H ₂ O)Cl]	–	3481 mb	3522 mb	1577 vs	1431 s	2048 vs	509 w	476 m	414 m
[Fe(MPAAP)(NO ₃) ₃ (H ₂ O)]	–	3392 mb	3392 mb	1593 vs	1444 s	–	470 w	430 m	354 m
[Fe(MPAAP) ₂ Br ₂]Br	–	3413 mb	–	1579 vs	1433 s	–	–	524 m	464 m
[Fe(MPAAP)(ClO ₄) ₃ (H ₂ O)]	–	3373 mb	3373 mb	1577 vs	1431 s	–	466 w	418 s	376 m

spectra of the nitrate complexes of GAAP and MPAAP are suggestive of monodentately coordinated nitrate group^{13,14} ($\nu_4 \sim 1485$, $\nu_1 \sim 1382$, $\nu_2 \sim 1026$ cm^{-1}) for GAAP complex; ($\nu_4 \sim 1517$, $\nu_1 \sim 1379$, $\nu_2 \sim 1024$ cm^{-1}) for MPAAP complex. The N-coordinated nature^{12,13} of the thiocyanate group in GAAP complex is indicated by $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ (~ 2050 cm^{-1}), $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ (~ 765 cm^{-1}) and δ_{NCS} (~ 507 cm^{-1}). The N-coordinated nature of the thiocyanate group in MPAAP complex¹²⁻¹⁴ is indicated by the $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ (~ 2048 cm^{-1}), $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ (~ 769 cm^{-1}) and δ_{NCS} (~ 476 cm^{-1}). The bands at 1186 cm^{-1} (ν_4), 1097 cm^{-1} (ν_1) and 622 cm^{-1} (ν_3) in the spectra of perchlorato complex of GAAP are suggestive of monodentate coordination^{13,15}. Also the bands at 1139 cm^{-1} (ν_4), 1087 cm^{-1} (ν_1) and 626 cm^{-1} (ν_3) in the spectra of perchlorato complex of MPAAP are suggestive of monodentate coordination^{13,15}.

There is a medium broad band (~ 3522 – 3373 cm^{-1}) in nitrate, perchlorato and thiocyanato MPAAP complexes. This band may be an indication of coordinated water. In nitrate and perchlorato complexes this band is appeared to be collinear with the stretching frequency of phenol moiety. Two other weak bands ~ 900 cm^{-1} and (740 – 650 cm^{-1}) are assignable to rocking and wagging modes of water is supportive for the presence of coordinated water^{27,28,30}.

The chloro complex of MPAAP showed a strong band ~ 352 cm^{-1} which is characteristic for bridging chlorine, (μ -Cl), between two iron atoms. A new non-ligand absorption ~ 376 cm^{-1} is also attributed to $\nu_{\text{Fe-Cl}}$ stretch of this complex^{11,31}.

The electronic spectral bands of two ligands are almost similar. Both of them have bands around 380 nm and 1420 nm are attributed to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. In the spectra of the complexes, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions exhibited at slightly lower value. The spectra of all the complexes exhibited low intensity broad bands in the region 440 nm to 526 nm can be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$ (G) and around 558 nm to 607 nm can be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (G) transitions⁶⁻⁸.

The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectrum of the ligand GAAP shows three singlets^{17,18} at δ 2.7–2.98, 3.05–3.39 and 3.83–3.91 ppm corresponds to methyl protons of $>\text{C-CH}_3$, $>\text{N-CH}_3$ and $-\text{OCH}_3$ respectively. The signal due to five aromatic protons of the antipyrine phenyl ring appear as multiplet between δ 7.38–7.59 ppm and those due to protons of phenyl ring of phenol moiety are observed as multiplet between δ 6.85–6.88 ppm. The signal due to

phenolic $-\text{OH}$ proton appears as hump¹⁶ at δ 5.56 ppm.

In the ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectrum of the ligand MPAAP shows three singlets^{17,18} at δ 2.65–2.87, 3.23–3.41 and 3.81–3.92 ppm corresponds to the signals of methyl protons of $>\text{C-CH}_3$, $>\text{N-CH}_3$, $-\text{OCH}_3$ respectively. The signal due to five aromatic protons of the phenyl ring of antipyrine moiety appear as multiplet between δ 6.38–7.69 ppm and those due to protons of phenyl ring of phenol moiety appear as multiplet between δ 6.38–6.52 ppm. The signal due to phenolic $-\text{OH}$ proton appears at δ 8.06 ppm is assigned to hydrogen bonded phenolic proton^{13,17}.

Thermal behavior of the complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{MPAAP})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$ was studied by TGA in air at a heating rate of 10 $^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ conjunction with DTG (Fig. 2). The complex undergoes a two stage decomposition as indicated by DTG peaks, 313 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 457 $^\circ\text{C}$.

The TG curve shows a second plateau after 600 $^\circ\text{C}$. This indicates completion of the decomposition. The stage of decomposition initiates at 90 $^\circ\text{C}$ and occurs at (110 – 380 $^\circ\text{C}$) is due to the mass loss of coordinated water, a chlorine moiety, two thiocyanate moiety and a part of the ligand, making a total mass loss 52.94%. The decomposition continues with a gradual decrease in weight and at (390 – 600 $^\circ\text{C}$), with a mass loss of 29.08% is due to decomposition of the remaining part of the ligand and it is finally undergone oxidative decomposition to Fe_2O_3 . The residual mass is about 14.28% (theoretical –14.17%) which has been assigned to the oxidative decomposition to give Fe_2O_3 as the ultimate residue. The percentage of coordinated water from TGA is found to be 3.29% and that calculated theoretically is 3.20%. The TG and DTG peaks suggest the mass loss of coordinated water occurs²⁷ at 196 $^\circ\text{C}$.

Both decomposition stages obey Coats-Redfern equation^{9,10}. The correlation coefficient for the first stage was found to be 0.9928 and that of the second stage, 0.954. The activation energy E , for these two stages were 38.38 kJ mol^{-1} and 41.49 kJ mol^{-1} respectively. The ΔS values, -225 kJ mol^{-1} and -222.46 JK mol^{-1} suggests the instability of both the decomposition stages^{19,26}. The negative ΔS value also indicates that the activated complex has more ordered structure than the reactants and the reactions are slower than the normal²⁹.

X-Ray powder diffraction patterns (Fig. 3) of the complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{MPAAP})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$ has been carried out

Fig. 2. TG and DTG curve of $[\text{Fe}(\text{MPAAP})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$

Fig. 3. X-Ray diffraction pattern of $[\text{Fe}(\text{MPAAP})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$

using $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation with $\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$ and was indexed using Hesse and Lipson's procedure⁵⁻⁷. The results (Table 3) show that the complex belongs to the ortho-

rhombic crystal system²⁰, having unit cell dimensions, $a = 6.0330 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 7.3207 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 12.8374 \text{ \AA}$.

The electrochemical behavior of the complex

Line	<i>hkl</i>	$\sin^2 \theta$ (obs)	$\sin^2 \theta$ (cal)	Relative intensity
1	011	0.0139	0.0146	14.84
2	011	0.0151	0.0146	67.76
3	101	0.0212	0.0199	32.00
4	012	0.0263	0.0254	79.22
5	110	0.0279	0.0273	36.29
6	102	0.0301	0.0307	32.17
7	020	0.0449	0.0443	100.00
8	022	0.0553	0.0586	28.22
9	121	0.0632	0.0641	19.93
10	122	0.0726	0.0749	7.23

$[\text{Fe}_2(\text{MPAAP})_2\text{Cl}_6]$ was studied using cyclic voltammetry at a scan rate of 100 mV s^{-1} after deaerating 10^{-3} M solution of the complex in acetonitrile with tetrabutyl ammoniumhexafluorophosphate as the supporting electrolyte. The cyclic voltammogram of the complex shows the reduction and oxidation of iron(III) in the complex and is characterized by a well defined peak. The redox processes were $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$ with quasi reversible peaks^{21,22}, with potential E_{pa} , -354 mV and E_{pc} , -646 mV (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammogram of $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{MPAAP})_2\text{Cl}_6]$.

The FAB-mass spectrum of iron(III) complex, $[\text{Fe}(\text{GAAP})(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}_2]$ showed the characteristic molecular ion peak at m/z 1524, which corresponds to the molecular weight of the complex. The other important peaks are due to the formation of various radicals such as (Cl^\bullet) ,

(NCS^\bullet) , (N^\bullet) , $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{OH.OCH}_3^\bullet)$, $[\text{CH}_3\text{N}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)\text{NCO}^\bullet]$, and (CH_3^\bullet) . The fragmentation pattern²³, showing the structure of the complex is given in Scheme 1.

Based on the analytical, spectral (IR, UV-Visible, FAB-mass), magnetic, thermal, electrochemical data, an octahedral structure (Figs. 5a and 5b) is tentatively proposed for Fe^{III} GAAP complexes and Fe^{III} MPAAP complexes.

The computer models (molecular modeling) of the suggested configuration of the ligands GAAP, MPAAP and the complexes $[\text{Fe}(\text{GAAP})(\text{Cl}_3)]$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{MPAAP})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$ were constructed using the software Hyperchem³². The energy minimized model from the geometry optimization are presented (Figs. 6 and 7).

Experimental

4-Aminoantipyrine (Fluka, Switzerland), Guaiacol, 3-methoxyphenol (Lobachemie, Mumbai) were used as supplied. All other chemicals including iron(III) salts were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of the ligands :

The ligands were synthesized from 4-aminoantipyrine and 2-methoxyphenol (Guaiacol)/3-methoxyphenol as the case may be, by diazotization and coupling as described in the literature²⁵.

Preparation of iron(III) thiocyanate :

30 ml of an aqueous solution of ferric chloride was mixed with 70 ml of an aqueous solution of 10% potassium thiocyanate. The deep red iron(III) thiocyanate was extracted into ether layer by vigorous shaking of the aqueous solution with ether in a separating funnel. The ether layer was collected and dried in a desiccator using anhydrous CaCl_2 . This solution was used for the preparation of iron(III) thiocyanate complexes³.

Preparation of iron(III) perchlorate :

Iron(III) perchlorate was prepared³ from metal carbonate and perchloric acid (Aldrich & Wilson Ltd., England). The carbonate was dissolved in hot 60% perchloric acid. A slight excess of metal carbonate was used. The undissolved salt was removed by filtration. The filtrate was evaporated to get the perchlorate and the metal perchlorate obtained was recrystallised from hot water

and was used for the synthesis of perchlorate complex of iron(III) with MPAAP ligand.

Preparation of iron(III) bromide :

Iron(III) bromide was prepared from the metal carbonate and 60% hydrobromic acid. The metal carbonate was dissolved in 60% hydrobromic acid. A slight excess of metal carbonate was used. The undissolved salt was removed by filtration. The filtrate was kept in a desiccator for few weeks to get anhydrous iron(III) bromide.

Preparation of the complexes :

Following general method was adopted for the preparation of the complexes. Hot methanolic solution (30 ml) of the metal salt (2.5 mmol) was added gradually to a hot solution of the ligand (2.5 mmol) in the same solvent (30 ml) with constant stirring and then refluxed for 4–5 h on a water bath. Then it was slowly cooled and allowed to stand for 4–5 days. The solid complex obtained was filtered, washed successively with aqueous methanol fol-

Fig. 5a. Proposed structures for the Fe^{III} complexes.

lowed by ether-benzene mixture. It was then dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*. Yield 65%.

The metal, halogen and perchlorate were estimated by

standard methods²⁴. Microanalysis (CHNS) were performed at STIC, Kochi, Kerala.

The IR spectra of the ligands and their iron(III) com-

$[\text{Fe}(\text{MPAAP})_2\text{Br}_2]\text{Br}$

$[\text{Fe}(\text{MPAAP})(\text{Y})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{X}]$, (X = Cl, Y = NCS)

Fig. 5b. Proposed structures for the Fe^{III} complexes.

plexes were recorded in the region, 4000–400 cm^{-1} on a JASCO FTIR 430 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. The ^1H NMR spectra of the ligands were recorded in CDCl_3 on a 300 MHz (Bruker Advance dP α -300) FTNMR instrument using TMS as reference. The electronic spectra were recorded in the solid state by reflectance method on a Varian Cary 5E UV-Vis-NIR spectrometer.

FAB-mass spectrum of the complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{GAAP})(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}_2]$ was recorded on a Joel SX 102/Da-600 mass spectrometer/Data System using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the spectrum was recorded at room temperature. *m*-Nitro benzyl alcohol (NBA) was used as the matrix.

Magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes at room temperature (300 ± 3 K) were measured on a magnetic susceptibility balance, Sherwood Scientific, Cambridge, UK. Diamagnetic corrections (χ_{Dia}) for various atoms and structural units were computed using Pascal constants².

GAAP

Fig. 6. Energy optimized configuration of GAAP and $[\text{Fe}(\text{GAAP})\text{Cl}_3]$.

MPAAP

Fig. 7. Energy optimized configuration of MPAAP and $[\text{Fe}(\text{MPAAP})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$.

Thermal analysis of the complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{MPAAP})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$ was carried out by TG and DTG techniques in static air at a heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$.

Cyclic voltammetric profile of the complex $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{MPAAP})_2\text{Cl}_6]$ was run on BAS-CV-50W voltammetric analyzer, using glassy carbon as working electrode

X-Ray powder diffraction patterns of the complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{MPAAP})(\text{NCS})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$ was also carried out on Philips X-ray diffractometer (PW1710) using $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation with $\lambda = 1.5405\text{ \AA}$ and was indexed using Hesse and Lipson's procedure²⁰

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